

Research Article

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Emerging political stalwarts of Sisaala land: Biographical narratology of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia's personality dispositions

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Abstract: In the Ghanaian political landscape, Sisaala land is on record to have produced political stalwarts who have occupied high-ranking political portfolios including the presidency of Ghana. Previous research has identified some pioneering Sisaala political stalwarts including; Dr. Hilla Limman, Imoro Egala; and others. Also, prominent political stalwarts such as; Kwame Nkrumah, Kofi Abrefa Busia, Simon Diedong Dombo, Adu Boahen, Jerry John Rawlings, and others have been variously studied by biographers. Motivated by previous biographical studies anchored on the paucity of similar biographies on emerging political stalwarts of Sisaala land, the study utilised qualitative narrative design to chronicle the biography, personality dispositions, and developmental contributions of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia. Empirical data were elicited through semi-structured interviews from twenty-one (21) heterogeneous-purposively

sampled respondents. The study found Chinnia to be a growing academic, known staunch member of the New Patriotic Party and a potential political stalwart in Ghana who currently serves as the Member of Parliament for Sissala East Constituency and Deputy Minister of Sanitation and Water Resources. With mixed viewpoints ably argued by the research participants, the study further found Chinnia to be a development-oriented personality with dispositions that are in tandem with the five-factor personality model (emotional intelligence, assertiveness, openness, conscientiousness, & loyalty). With his enviable academic pedigree, development-mindedness, political activism and unwavering personality dispositions, Chinnia appears to have a brighter political future. For Chinnia to consolidate his political growth, and fortunes, he should promote his positive personality dispositions while working on his weaknesses; unite the rank and file of his party in the Sissala East Constituency, address the major developmental needs of his constituents, and loyally support his party-led government to deliver its mandate to Ghanaians as promised.

Keywords – Amidu Issahaku Chinnia, Emerging political stalwarts, Personality dispositions, Sisaala land, Sissala east constituency

1. INTRODUCTION

Sisaala (corrupted as Sissala) people live in all parts of Ghana. However, the geographical origin of the Sisaala people is located in the Guinea Savannah Zone of Ghana (Issaka, Buri, Tobita, Nakamura & Owusu-Adjei, 2012). In clearer descriptive terms, Sisaala land is situated at the northmost part of the Upper West Region of Ghana

spanning from the fringes of Ghana's international boundary with Burkina Faso and cascading to the internal regional borders with parts of Upper East Region and Northeast Region. Predominantly, Sisaala people are agriculturalists and linguistically classified under the Mabia (Gur)-speaking people of the larger Grusi (Gurune/Grunshi) ethnic group (Kwekudee, 2013). Although Sisaala forms part of the larger Grusi ethnic group, Sisaala people have their unique language known as Sisaali/isaali. Out of the existing eleven (11) Municipalities/Districts within the Upper West Region of northern Ghana, the Sisaala land wholly and partly covers one municipality and three districts. These include; Sissala East Municipality, Sissala West District, Wa East District, Lambusie District, and parts of Daffiama Busie Issah District. Each of these districts is blessed with lots of potential and already known tourists sites such as; slave defense wall in Gwollu; the tomb of late President Dr. Hilla Limann in Gwollu; the traditional bone setting centre in Gwollu, Wotuomo magical cave located between Danji and Lilixia, hunter's footprints on a mysterious rock at Dolibizon, mysterious rocks at Pieng, mysterious River at *Nmanduanu*, the white man's grave at Tumu and many others (Kwekudee, 2013).

In the Ghanaian political landscape, the Sisaala land is on record, both nationally and internationally, to have produced political stalwarts who in the past and present have occupied high ranking political portfolios including the presidency of Ghana. In a biographical study, Damwah (2011) detailed the life and times of Dr. Hilla Limman (of blessed memory), the third democratically elected president of Ghana, who hailed from the Sisaala land (Gwollu) in the Upper West Region of Ghana. In that study, Damwah (2011) identifies other pioneering Sisaala political stalwarts such as; Alidu Kanton - Member of the Legislative Assembly from 1951 to 1954; Imoro Egala - elected Member of Parliament (MP) for the Tumu constituency in the 1954 parliamentary election in Northern Territorial Ghana as well as Minister of Health; Mumuni Dimmie - elected Member of Parliament of the Tumu constituency in the 1956 elections, and others. Other Biographical studies have revealed prominent Ghanaian political stalwarts such as; Joseph Boakye Danquah, Kwame Nkrumah, Kofi Abrefa Busia, Simon Diedong Dombo, Adu Boahen, J.A. Ankrah, Jerry John Rawlings, Evans Atta Mills; I. K. Acheampong; John Agyekum Kufuor; and many others (Ashong, 2019; Anti, 2016; Dartey-Baah, 2015; Ibrahim, 2014; Adedeji, 2001; Biney, 2007). These biographical studies highlight the case that the life histories of such political stalwarts are inseparable from Ghana's political struggle for independence, democratic rule, and national development (Ashong, 2019). Ashong avers that biographical studies have been part of the nation-building project, intended to inspire, to show what was accomplished by who and how, and to install feelings of patriotism by encouraging readers to identify with the researched. Motivated by the aforementioned previous biographical studies that chronicled the lives, times, and developmental contributions of distinguished Ghanaian political stalwarts, the current study is anchored on the paucity of similar biographical studies on emerging political stalwarts of Sisaala land. Given this, the study sought to chronicle the biography of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia, emphasising his unique personality traits and key contributions to national development as a young political activist.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1. Theoretical framework

The study was grounded on Gordon Allport's dispositional theory propounded in 1937. Gordon Allport was a renowned psychologist known to have pioneered a study on human personality traits also termed as the dispositional theory. According to Allport (1937), human traits are essentially unique to each individual and relate to the set of unique characteristics possessed in an individual's life. Although Allport identified an unlimited number of potential traits that could define the personality of an individual, personality traits could be categorised into three broad segments (Allport, 1937). These include; cardinal traits which are pervasive and dominant traits that practically define the life of an individual (greed, heroic, sadism, religious, hardworking, stalwart, and others); central traits on the other hand are the major characteristics used to describe a person and form the basic foundations or the building blocks of the personality of an individual such as; smart, dumb, wild, shy, sneaky,

dopey, grumpy and others, whereas, secondary traits are those that are not quite obvious or consistent. Preferences, attitudes, situational traits all fall within secondary traits. In addition to Allport's personality dispositional (trait) theory, the study was further situated within the five-factor (Big five) personality model which is categorised in contemporary psychology as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, and neuroticism and consensually adopted to describe the most salient features of human personality (Goldberg, 1990; John & Srivastava, 1999; Zaidi, Wajid, Zaidi, Zaidi, & Zaidi, 2013; Grankvist & Kajonius, 2015; Glicksohn, & Naor-Ziv, 2016; Simic & Ristic, 2017; Anwar, Xiao, Xi'an, Fiaz, Ikram & Younas, 2017; Kajonius, 2021). Therefore, Allport's personality dispositional (trait) theory supported by the five-factor (Big five) personality model, as espoused, suitably grounded the study given the case that the study focused on revealing the biography and personality traits of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia as a known young political activist in the Sisaala land of northern Ghana.

2.2. Stalwart defined

The term stalwart has received wider and specific interpretations. Most of these definitions of the term, stalwart, largely mean the same thing. According to vocabulary.com (2021), to be stalwart is to be loyal, no matter the circumstances. In a corroborated viewpoint, stalwart relates to loyal, especially for a long time; able to be trusted; committed; dedicated; devoted; faithful; firm (certain); staunch; steadfast; approving; steady; true (sincere); unfaltering; unshakeable; unswerving; and unwavering (Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary & Thesaurus, 2021; Wikipedia, 2021). A stalwart is someone who is steadfast or someone with an uncompromising partisan stance (Infoplease, 2021). In the contextual milieu of this study, the term stalwart refers to the admirable personality of a politician with traits such as; loyalty, trustworthiness, hardworking, firmness, sincerity, and others that are being exhibited toward a particular political party and society and/or a nation, for which reason, such a person is nationally recognised across the political divide and has ever been entrusted with high ranking public leadership position/s whether by election and/or appointment.

2.3. Empirical review of biographical studies on Ghanaian political stalwarts

Biographical studies are grounded in research. According to Ashong, (2019: 1), "biographical studies seem to have arrested the attention of scholars in the past few decades or so." They are written narratives of a person's life history (Rosenthal, 2004; Bornat, 2007; Moulin, 2015; Ashong, 2019; Essel & Asare, 2020), mostly, the life and works of prominent academics and politicians (Ashong, 2019; Kwapong, 2016; Anti, 2016; Addae-Mensah, 2010; Lodge, 2006). In Ghana, prominent political stalwarts such as; Joseph Boakye Danquah, Kwame Nkrumah, Kofi Abrefa Busia, Kwegyir Aggrey, Simon Diedong Dombo, Hilla Limann, Adu Boahen, and many others, have received biographical studies (Ashong, 2019; Anti, 2016; Dartey-Baah, 2015; Ibrahim, 2014; Damwah, 2011; Biney, 2007; Adedeji, 2001) which have placed such individuals in the context of Ghana's political struggle for independence, democracy and national development (Anti, 2016). Biney's (2007) study examines Nkrumah's life, thought, controversies with the British colonial authorities from 1951 to 1957; politics in the post-independence period and Nkrumah's economic, cultural and foreign policies; the aftermath of the overthrow of Nkrumah in February 1966, and Nkrumah's legacies in Ghana and Africa. Biney (2007) concludes that Kwame Nkrumah, the first democratically elected president of the first republic of Ghana, remains a towering figure not only in Ghana but in African history for the enthusiastic roles he played in leading Ghana to independence in 1957 and subsequently redefining Ghana as a beacon of hope in Africa. It was typified that Nkrumah's uncompromising concept of Pan-Africanist ideology led to the formation and transformation of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) into the African Union (AU) which is one of Nkrumah's legacies (Biney, 2007). Nkrumah is reported to have adopted socialist economic, positive neutrality and non-alignment strategies as intellectual positions to navigate his way in a "Cold War world and maintain friendships with both the USSR [Union of Soviet Socialist Republic] and the West whilst maintaining Ghana's and Africa's national interests" (Biney, 2007: 288). Dartey-Baah (2015), Okon (2014) and

Botwe-Asamoah (2005) in their biographical studies consensually agree with Biney, that Nkrumah's political stalwartness is known globally for his unrelenting political struggles that led to his final declaration of Ghana's independence on 6th March, 1957, and his leading pan Africanist role in the formation of OAU, now AU. Another key legacy of Kwame Nkrumah as noted by Botwe-Asamoah (2005: 64) is that Nkrumah's, "rebirth of African culture meant the abrogation of the colonial legacy in respect of African arts in the academy. He saw African art forms as an inseparable component of the struggle against colonial legacy" and therefore charged the "Institute of African Studies situated in Africa, to pay particular attention to the arts of Africa, for the study of these can enhance our understanding of African institutions and values, and the cultural bonds that unite us [Africans]". Also, studies have identified the personality traits of Nkrumah to be deeply rooted in the African culture, customs and traditions such as; his profound sense of humour, resilient and an unwavering personality; selfless and humble personality; thrift, hard work, honesty, sacrifice, devotion to duty which contributed to his charisma that saw him mingling with the non-elitists of the society, projecting him as the much-awaited messiah to lead the path toward the new political and administrative order sought for by the indigenous Gold Coast populace (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Biney, 2011; Iijima, 1998). However, one key weakness and principal contradiction in Nkrumah's political practice and thought was his resort to political repression of the opposition in his pursuit for national unity (Biney, 2007).

Also, the biography of Kofi Abrefa Busia (1969-1972) was studied by Dartey-Baah (2015) where it came to light that Busia may not have begun as a full-fledged politician but "the formation of the Progress Party brought Busia close to his political dream of forming a democratic government that could replace Nkrumah's government" (Ofori-Atta, 1978; as cited in Dartey-Baah, 2015: 55). Eventually, the "second republic administration of Ghana fell into the leadership arms of Busia when the National Liberation Council (NLC) handed over power to him" after Kwame Nkrumah was ousted in the 1966 coup d'état led by Colonel E. K. Kotoka and General A. A. Afrifa (Dartey-Baah, 2015: 55). Dartey-Baah further notes that Busia's role as the prime minister of Ghana was to ensure that Ghana returned to a democratic and liberal state which was evidenced in some of Busia's initial democratic policies and development plans such as "free society as well as egalitarian principles", and "*The Aliens Compliance Order of 18th November, 1969*" which was introduced as a result of the huge economic crises that plagued the economy, and also to create employment for the masses" (pp 55-56). However, though Busia started as a democratic leader, he veered more towards the authoritarian leadership approach which led to the end of his political leadership (Dartey-Baah, 2015).

On another breadth, the life of Dr. Hilla Limann (1979-1981) was chronicled by Damwah (2011), and Dartey-Baah (2015). Both aforementioned studies took critical look at the life, struggles, works, successes, and failures of Dr. Hilla Limann, president of the third Republic of Ghana. It was revealed that Limann, the founder of the People National Convention (PNC), was an academic, honest person, a gentleman - more of a diplomat than a politician and a democratic leader who was elected into office on the 24th of September 1979 (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Damwah, 2011). Limann "espoused the virtues of morality, had a great respect for good governance and abhorred corruption, selfishness and greed" and upheld freedom of speech of the people and of the press (Banamini, 2010; as cited in Dartey-Baah, 2015: 56). Dartey-Baah (2015: 56) exemplified that "as president he [Limann] personally wrote a letter to all his appointees reminding them of the code of conduct and beseeched them to shun ostentatious life-styles, but rather to live moderate lives". However, Limann's 27 months administration was truncated by another coup led by Flt. Lt. Jerry John Rawlings (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Damwah, 2011).

Biographical studies were equally conducted on the life and times of Jerry John Rawlings (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Adedeji, 2001). It was established that Jerry John Rawlings was a two-term democratically elected president (1993-2000) of the fourth republic administration of Ghana (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Adedeji, 2001). Until then, Rawlings was a "Flight Lieutenant in the Air Force and a militant populist when he led the June 4, 1979 coup that overthrew the regime of General Frederick William Kwasi Akuffo" (Dartey-Baah, 2015: 56; Adedeji, 2001: 1). It was further revealed that Rawlings' leadership style was a mixture of populism and authoritarianism, sometimes marked by

controversial pronouncements with the capacity to pull crowds and appealed to the ordinary man on the streets (Shillington, 1992; as cited in Dartey-Baah, 2015). Besides the deterring strives chalked against corruption, the biggest legacy of Rawlings' political achievement was his remarkable transition from military rule to a peaceful democratic succession (Duah, 2006; as cited in Dartey-Baah, 2015; Adedeji, 2001) which has since been ably continued by his successors.

In a scholarly biography, Ashong (2019) documents the life and times of Professor Emeritus Adu Boahen, his contributions to Ghanaian and African historiography, academic institutions, and professional associations. Ashong's study further examines Adu Boahen's place in Ghana's struggle for democracy and constitutional governance and concludes that "Adu Boahen was not just a renowned historian who contributed to pioneering Ghanaian and African historiography, but was also instrumental in attempts to consolidate democratic culture in Ghana" (Ashong, 2019: vi). Adu Boahen "advocated constitutional governance, the rule of law, sound democratic institutions, the freedom of the individual, freedom of the press, and a national economic development in which the private sector played a dominant role" for which reasons, his "life was an inspiration to many people including those of different political orientations (Ashong, 2019: 134). According to Ashong (2019: 135) Adu Boahen's sense of purpose, hard work, sheer determination, and democratic governance made him to be listed for conferment of the "Order of the Star of Ghana, the highest award given by the State to individuals who have contributed immensely to the country".

Another biographical study worthy of note was Ibrahim's (2014) study on the life and times of Naa (Chief) Simon Diedong Dombo. S. D. Dombo was an illustrious son of Duori in Jirapa Municipality of Upper West Region in Ghana. Ibrahim's study reveals that S.D. Dombo was a professional teacher, astute politician, and leading founder (first Chairperson) of Northern People Party (NPP), and one of the luckiest successors to the Duori Chieftaincy skin in March, 1949. In politics, it is reported that Dombo's political activism started when he was a teacher trainee in Government Training College in Tamale where he associated with the likes of B. K. Adama, Abayifaa Karbo, E. A. Mahama, Jato Kaleo, Yakubu Tali, Mumuni Bawumia and others (Ibrahim, 2014). Dombo later became an active member of the northern territories' council; was appointed member of the Legislative Council and later elected into the Legislative Assembly where he worked in advancing the course of the people of entire northern Ghana (Ibrahim, 2014). Bening (1990) notes that Dombo fronted "the fight for political, economic, social and educational interests in which the North lagged behind the South. In view of the greater need for development in the Protectorate, S. D. Dombo suggested a separate development plan for the region" (as cited in Ibrahim, 2014: 34). Some successes associated with the northern territories' council of which Dombo was an active member include; the establishment of the Special Northern Scholarship Scheme for people of northern Ghana; free boarding in all secondary schools, Training Colleges, and Higher Institutions situated in the North (Ibrahim, 2014). The political activism of S. D. Dombo from one party to another eventually won him the Jirapa-Lambusie Parliamentary seat from 1969 to 1972 on the ticket of the Progress Party where he was appointed as the Minister of Interior under Dr. K. A. Busia's administration (Ibrahim, 2014).

The empirical review of biographical studies on some prominent Ghanaian Politicians, as discussed, has not only revealed the lives and times of such individuals but has placed them in the context of Ghana's political struggle for independence, democratic rule, and pursuit of common national development agenda.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The study utilised qualitative biographical narrative design. Biographical narrative design is deployed for studies that focus on narration, life history, oral history, autobiography, biographical interpretive methods, storytelling, and ethnography (Rosenthal, 2004; Bornat, 2007; Moulin, 2015; Essel & Asare, 2020). Therefore, the adoption of qualitative biographical narrative design allowed the study to specifically narrate the life and personality

dispositions of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia while enumerating his contributions to national development as a political activist.

3.2 Population, sample and sampling technique

Population entails "the entire mass of observations, which is the parent group from which a sample is to be formed" (Pandey & Pandey, 2015: 40). In the light of this, the population of the study included; the nuclear and extended family members of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia; Chairpersons, Communication Officers and Elders of registered political parties in Sissala East Constituency, and Amidu Issahaku Chinnia himself. Since it was practically impossible to take a complete and comprehensive study of the entire population because of the nature and pattern of distribution or dispersion (Umar & Madugu, 2015), the heterogeneous purposive sampling technique was variously adopted to obtain seven (7) close family relatives of Chinnia; three (3) Constituency Chairpersons and three (3) Communication Officers of the three most pronounced political parties (New Patriotic Party, National Democratic Congress & People National Convention) in Sissala East Constituency; seven (7) Elders of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia's political party as well as Chinnia himself all amounting to a total sample size of twenty-one (21) respondents. The sampling of the enlisted respondents was premised on the case that they possess the best available knowledge on the biography and political activism of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia in their capacities as close family members, leading political actors who have directly and indirectly encountered Amidu Issahaku Chinnia in the political discourse of Sissala land. The inclusion of Chinnia's political opponents was to elicit heterogeneous views on the life, times, and personality of Chinnia as a politician.

3.3. Data collection procedure

The study utilised a semi-structured interview tool for data collection. The use of a semi-structured interview format ensured flexibility as it gave ample opportunities for the interviewees to freely express themselves while creating a convenient room for the interviewer to seek relevant clarifications using probes during the interview process (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018). The interviews were conducted at the participants' agreed social settings and convenience whereby all responses were tape-recorded for transcription.

3.4. Data analysis plan

Data analysis started with manual but diligent transcription of the interview contents whereby the texts of all the interview transcripts were closely examined and coded into themes. Discussion and analysis of the findings of the study were logically and thoroughly done using narrative and thematic analytical tools. During the discussion and analysis of the findings, the study adopted pseudonyms to conceal the actual names of the research participants. This was done in honour of a written consent entered into between the researcher and the research participants that demanded their anonymity and confidentiality be protected.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Biography and personality dispositions of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia

4.1.1. Biography (Family and Educational Background)

The biography of Chinnia was revealed by himself and adequately corroborated by his family member-respondents. Amidu Issahaku Chinnia (Figure 1), popularly referred to as Chinnia, is a young energetic Ghanaian who hails from Bugujan in the Sissala East Municipality in the Upper West Region of northern Ghana. Saato Issahaku (father) and Fati Issahaku (mother) who are both deceased, are the parents of Amidu Chinnia. He was born on 20th May 1978 in Techiman at the era when his father was teaching in Manso in the Bono East Region of Ghana. A few years after he was born, his father took an inter-regional transfer to the then newly created Upper West Region in the early 1980s where Chinnia got his basic education in Nabugujan in the then Sissala District (now Sissala East Municipal) from 1984 to 1994. Chinnia progressed to Tumu Secondary Technical School in 1994 where he offered General Agriculture as a programme and excelled in his final Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE) in 1996. Having excelled in the SSSCE, Chinnia continued his education at Nusrat Jahan

Ahmadiyya training College in Wa in 1997 and graduated in 2000 as a professional *Certificate A* teacher. Chinnia taught for three years at the basic school level and sought further studies in the Nyankpala campus of the University for Development Studies (UDS) in Tamale. In UDS, Chinnia offered a four-year Bachelor of Science degree in Agricultural Technology between 2003 and 2007. After successful completion of the programme, he was reposted by the Sissala East District Directorate of Ghana Education Service to head Tumu Junior Secondary School in Tumu township. As someone interested in academia, Chinnia, once again, enrolled in UDS (Nyankpala campus) for a Master of Philosophy degree in Horticulture and successfully graduated in 2020. While on the Master of Philosophy programme, Chinnia concurrently pursued a Bachelor of Laws (LLB) programme at the Central University College in Ghana from 2017-2020 and was successfully awarded an LLB degree. Although he is not yet a practising lawyer, Chinnia avered that he has partially attained one of his academic targets but with the vision of enrolling into the professional law course at Ghana School of law, Makola, in no distant future. This, he believed would contribute significantly to his political career. With religion and marital purviews, Amidu Issahaku Chinnia is a faithful Muslim and happily married to his lifetime pretty partner, Bipuah Sheitu, who are both blessed with four (4) brilliant children, as of the time the study was conducted.

Figure 1: Photograph of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia
(Source: Chinnia's Gallery, 2021).

4.1.2. Political activism of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia

The study ascertained that Amidu Issahaku Chinnia did not hail from a politically exposed nuclear family. Chinnia, corroborated by his family member-respondents, explained that his parents had no known partisan affiliations whatsoever but neither opposed nor suppressed his decision to join partisan activism. Narrating how and when he joined party politics, Chinnia revealed that although he was a die-hard supporter of the New Patriotic Party (NPP) since adolescence, he entered into full-time politics after he had completed Teacher Training College in 2000. This means that Chinnia's blending of the teaching profession with partisan politics is similar to the case of S D Dombo who was once a professional teacher and an astute politician (Ibrahim, 2014). Shortly after entering into full-time politics, Chinnia saw the urgency to rally youth support for the New Patriotic Party which appeared to be missing at the time due to the dominance of the People National Convention (PNC) and the competing force of the National Democratic Congress (NDC) in the Sisaala enclave. The political dominance herein intimated, particularly in the case of PNC, relates to the case that the third democratically elected president of the third republic of Ghana, Dr. Hilla Limann, of blessed memory, was of Sisaala origin and founder of PNC (Damwah, 2011). As a result, the Sisaala people at the time saw PNC as their bona fide political party. On the other hand, NDC which took over political reigns of the fourth republic of Ghana then had leading members, for instance, Alhaji Amin Amidu Sulemana, hailing from the Sisaala land. These leading members of NDC, at the time, had rapidly won the loyalty of many of the Sisaala people due to incumbency thereby positioning NDC as a competitive force to PNC while NPP remained an underdog in the Sisaala enclave. With this unfavourable political climate for NPP in the Sisaala

area, Chinnia explained that he took the boldest steps to form the Diglafuro youth wing of NPP in 2000 which drew all young patriots together under his interim chairmanship. This youth wing of NPP which was duly inaugurated by Chairman Abass Dauda-led NPP Constituency Executives was self-tasked to strategically market the New Patriotic Party to Sisaala people with the Diglafuro suburb of Tumu township been the starting point. Chinnia who was the first chairperson of the NPP Diglafuro Youth Wing asserted that the formation of the youth wing became the turning point of the NPP in the Sisaala enclave as it worked to popularise NPP fortunes in Ghana's 2000 general elections amidst the domineering PNC and NDC political activism in the Sisaala land. Amidu Chinnia highlighted that:

When I formed the Diglafuro NPP youth wing, we became a vibrant political force to reckon with particularly during the 2000 general elections. We were at the helm of affairs trying to galvanise votes for the NPP. PNC and NDC posed serious electoral threats to us [NPP] because they were more popular in the Sisaala area than the NPP. Due to this, our performance in the 2000 general elections was not too good. However, we have since mobilised a lot of support for the party to the extent that NPP has made electoral gains including winning parliamentary seats in the Sisaala area which hitherto alternated between PNC and NDC.

Chinnia further posits that the originating Executive Committee Members of the Diglafuro NPP Youth Wing have all risen through grassroots political structures to the forefront of NPP in the Sissala East Constituency. "...For instance, Tahiru Suara who was the secretary to the group is the current NPP constituency chairperson; the organiser then, Mohadeen, is now the Sissala East constituency organiser of NPP" (A. I. Chinnia, personal communication, June 9, 2021). Chinnia who founded and chaired the Diglafuro NPP Youth Wing was later appointed as the Assistant Constituency Secretary of NPP of then Sisaala Constituency between 2001 and 2003. He later contested, won and retained the NPP Constituency Secretary portfolio of Sisaala Constituency (which later became Sissala East Constituency) from 2003 to 2011. Although Chinnia resigned to contest the party's 2008 parliamentary primary, he lost the primary and was re-elected in 2009 to continue his constituency secretaryship position until he voluntarily stepped aside in 2011 to concentrate on his parliamentary ambition. While serving as the constituency secretary, Chinnia concurrently became the Public Relations Officer of Tertiary students' confederation (TESCON) of NPP from 2003-2004 when he was enrolled for his undergraduate studies in Nyankpala Campus of UDS. He later rose to become the NPP TESCON President of the same university from 2006-2007. At the period that Chinnia was at the helm of students' politics in the Nyankpala Campus of UDS, he was fortunate to have been appointed by the John Agyekum Kuffuor NPP-led government to serve as an Assembly Member of then Sisaala East District Assembly between 2005 to 2008. The recognition and appointment of Amidu Chinnia were probably premised on his pronounced political activism in ensuring the NPP gained grounds and curtailed the political dominance enjoyed by PNC and NDC in the Sisaala enclave. The political exposures of Chinnia ranging from the formation and chairmanship of Diglafuro NPP Youth Wing; as constituency executive; public relation officer and later President of TESCON – UDS; and having served as an appointed Assembly Member of the Sissala District Assembly prepared him with the right frame of political pedigree and the exigency to contest the NPP parliamentary primary in 2008. Although he marginally lost that primary, Chinnia remobilised himself, contested and won the subsequent NPP parliamentary primary to become the NPP Parliamentary Candidate for the Sisaala East Constituency in the 2012 Parliamentary Election in Ghana. Unfortunately, Amidu Issahaku Chinnia lost that election to the NDC candidate.

However, this did not dash his parliamentary ambitions in any way as he re-strategised, contested the 2015 parliamentary primary of NPP but lost that internal election to Ridwan Abass Dauda who subsequently won the Sissala East Parliamentary seat with the NPP also winning the 2016 Presidential Election. The victory of the 2016 presidential election by the NPP gave Chinnia political elevation as he was appointed by President Nana Addo Dankwa Akufo-Addo to serve the high office of Deputy Upper West Regional Ministerial portfolio from 2017 to

2020. While serving as the Deputy Upper West Regional Minister, Chinnia utilised every opportunity at his disposal to rejuvenate confidence in the rank and file of the NPP in the Sissala East constituency. This led to his victory of NPP 2020 Parliamentary primary against the sitting Member of Parliament, Ridwan Abass Dauda, and proceeded to retain the Sisaala East parliamentary seat for NPP. The NPP-respondents, when contacted, affirmed the political activism of Chinnia as espoused and stressed that, irrespective of regional, ethnic and other considerations in the president's appointments, Chinnia's ability to retain the Sisaala East parliamentary seat coupled with his longstanding political activism and loyalty (Figure 3) to the progress of NPP earned him the two terms appointment to serve as the Deputy Minister of Upper West Region, and Deputy Minister of Sanitation and Water Resources under the governorship of Nana Addo Dankwa Akufo-Addo. The NPP respondents concluded by arguing that the political growth of Chinnia from grassroot to national limelight as a Deputy Minister of state and government's regular communicator appearing on national media (television, radio & print) provides him a fertile political platform to leverage on and would soon attain the status of the Limanns, Dombos, Nkrumah's, Busias Boahens and others. However, Chinnia's political opponents, when interviewed, argued that though Chinnia is a staunch member of NPP for which reason he was appointed twice by President Nana Addo, his political prominence is limited to the NPP and could not be compared with any of the nationally known political stalwarts (Nkrumah, Rawlings, Limann & others)-"he needs to do more to get there". One of Chinnia's political opponents further claimed that Chinnia's two-term deputy ministerial appointments by President Akufo Addo were due to his closed relationship with the president (Figure 2) who runs family and friends government and that Chinnia's political career would come to an end when the president's tenure of office ends in 2024. It was also variously claimed by Chinnia's political opponents that Chinnia's irreparably divorced relationship with one of his leading closed associates and political tacticians during processes leading to the appointment of the Municipal Chief Executive for Sissala East Municipality in 2021 would haunt him(Chinnia) to their advantage in the 2024 parliamentary election. Per the discussion, it is clear that Chinnia is a nationally recognised staunch member of NPP, an emerging political stalwart but not fully riped to be generally referred to as a fullfledged nationally recognised political stalwart across the political divide in Ghana.

Figure 2: President Akufo Addo (left) having tete-a-tete with Chinnia (right) at a programme (Source: Chinnia's Gallery, 2021)

Figure 3: Chinnia Addressing a group of journalists after a political rally (Source: Chinnia's Gallery, 2021)

4.2. Personality dispositions of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia

Personality dispositions (traits) pertain to the unique observable but consistent behavioural attributes that define the generality of an individual. They represent the enduring patterns of thoughts, feelings, characteristics and behaviours that distinguish one individual from another (Allport, 1937; Roberts & Mroczek, 2008; Belcher, Volkow, Moeller & Ferré, 2014; Grankvist & Kajonius, 2015; Kurtulmuş, Katrinli & Katrinli, 2019). In this study, it was established that Amidu Issahaku Chinnia possessed diverse personality traits that serve as fertile grounds for his

political growth and development. Amongst the many personality traits recounted about Chinnia, the study found five of them to be cardinal as such dispositions (emotional intelligence, assertiveness, openness, conscientiousness, and loyalty) were consistently mentioned and largely justified by Chinnia's NPP-respondent with some of them strongly rebutted by Chinnia's political opponent-respondents. The aforementioned five cardinal personality traits of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia, as argued for and/or against by the respondents, are in tandem with the five-factor (Big Five) personality traits (Extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness or agreeableness and neuroticism) which are consensually observed as the most salient features of human personality (Goldberg, 1990; John & Srivastava, 1999; Zaidi, Wajid, Zaidi, Zaidi, & Zaidi, 2013; Grankvist & Kajonius, 2015; Glicksohn, & Naor-Ziv, 2016; Simic & Ristic, 2017; Anwar, Xiao, Xi'an, Fiaz, Ikram & Younas, 2017; Kajonius, 2021).

4.2.1. Emotional intelligence

The narrative proffered by Amidu Chinnia on how he has over the years handled politically induced provocations and irritations from intra-inter-political party brokers and the generality of his social engagements with people demonstrates that he is emotionally stable though much is still expected of him as ascertained by the study. The NPP-informants and Chinnia's family members largely, except two respondents, corroborated that Chinnia's consistent exhibition of emotional stability in most of his social and political engagements, even when he was a young politician in the early 2000s up-to-date, admirably revealed his emotionally intelligent personality. In emphasising Chinnia's resilience and time-tested emotional stability, one of the NPP-informant in Sissala East Constituency illustrated that:

Amidu Chinnia is calm and collected even when provoked. People wanted to take advantage of his youthful age to provoke unhealthy emotional outbursts in him when, in 2012, he became the NPP parliamentary candidate for Sissala East Constituency. He maintained his cool temperament no matter the level of provocations and disappointments from both within his party and amongst his political opponents. When he lost that election, he controlled his emotions without pointing fingers at those who vehemently thwarted his political progress even though he knew some of them. His ability to control his emotions and that of his supporters after the 2012 parliamentary election was a clear exhibition of his maturity and emotional intelligence. In my opinion, Chinnia's continuous exhibition of emotional intelligence on anger-provoking issues is one of the reasons he is rising in the political landscape both at the constituency, regional and national levels. (NPP-informant 1, personal communications, June 11, 2021)

However, views elicited from leading members of Chinnia's opposition parties (NDC & PNC) in the Sissala East Constituency suggest otherwise. They variously argued that Chinnia has not demonstrated resilient emotional intelligence in his political activism, particularly his reactions to issues on social media (Facebook). The aforementioned views expressed by Chinnia's opponents are consistent with that of the two patriots of Chinnia herein revealed. In their various vehemently stressed opinions, they argued that until Chinnia, as a public figure, desisted from public emotional outbursts on opposing views and trivialities from attention seekers, he could not be passed of being emotionally stable.

4.2.2. Assertiveness

Another outstanding disposition of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia, as revealed by the study, is his assertive personality. Although Chinnia (the researched) found it difficult to describe what people make of his approach to social and political issues, he opined that he has always considered the feelings and views of others in all his endeavours. In authenticating whether or not Chinnia has an assertive personality disposition as disclosed by himself, all the NPP-respondents and Chinnia's family member-respondents contacted by the study affirmed that Amidu Chinnia is someone with assertive and convincing communication skills. One of the NPP elders (personal communications, June 11, 2021) emphasised that:

...that young man [Chinnia] is highly assertive. He is always able to disseminate his message while respecting the rights and views of others. He is an excellent orator I should say. You know, when God gives you a talent, no one can take it away from you. Such is the case of the young man [Chinnia]. It is not only about his effective communication skills, but his warmth and positive approach to issues make him a distinct young politician. I am not a prophet, but I dare say that, if Chinnia could sustain his composure, he would steadily progress through the rank and file of NPP to become the president of the Republic of Ghana in the future, and for that matter, the second Sisaala native to assume the seat of Ghana's presidency after Dr. Hillia Limann.

Also, Chinnia's political opponent-respondents largely agreed on the assertive nature of Chinnia as observed in his political communications, radio and Televised political talk shows but accused Chinnia of sometimes trying to impose his views on others or many a time, he churns out mischief and propaganda. But in principle, all respondents consented that Chinnia is assertive and a smart communicator who takes advantage of available gaps to market himself and his political party. The description of Chinnia as someone with assertive personality trait is well within the extraversion dimension of the Big Five personality model and a very strong and consistent predictor of good leadership traits (Blickle, Meurs, Wihler, Ewen, Merkl & Missfeld, 2015 as cited in Kurtuluş, Katrinli & Katrinli, 2019; Anwar, Xiao, Xi'an, Fiaz, Ikram & Younas, 2017).

4.2.3. Openness/Agreeableness

The study further found Amidu Issahaku Chinnia to be a communitarian who is inherently open, modest, approachable, and generally agreeable to everybody irrespective of one's political lineage, religious orientation and social status. All the respondents, including Amidu Chinnia's political opponents, congruently intimated that the open and agreeable nature of Chinnia is uncontested and has remained a strong pillar resuscitating his continuous relevance in party political discourse in the Sisaala area, Upper West Region and Ghana by extension. According to A. I. Chinnia (personal communications, June 9, 2021):

To be a good politician is to be down to earth. Throughout my political life, I have done everything humanly possible to be open and agreeable to everybody, in terms of providing assistance, listening, adapting, and adopting dissenting views and ideas of others. Because of my openness, I can comfortably say that lots of leading members of opposing political parties and others have come to me for assistance and I have also consulted some of such people on other matters. So, my door is always widely opened to all, a good number of my constituents can attest to this.

Chinnia's political opponent-respondents variously indicated that Chinnia's open nature and ability to relate well with many Sisaala people across the political divide is a strength that continues to make him politically relevant. One of Chinnia's political opponent-respondents (personal communication, Match 14, 2022) revealed that "...Chinnia's ability to mingle with the grassroots and youth; his selfless support for Sissala people across the political divide when he was Deputy Upper West Regional Minister, won him the Sissala East Parliamentary seat in the 2020 parliamentary election". Amidu Chinnia's ability to mingle with grassroots and the youth (Figure 4A & B) as ascertained by the study is reflective of one of the ethical personality traits of Kwame Nkrumah and Jerry John Rawlings as revealed by literature (Dartey-Baah, 2015; Biney, 2011). However, Chinnia's political opponent-respondents variously pointed out that they had discovered this tricky trait of Chinnia and would snatch the seat from him in the upcoming 2024 Ghanaian general elections since Chinnia and his NPP-led government had failed Ghanaians with no developmental records to account to the people.

Figure 4 (A&B): Chinnia (at the foreground in yellowish long sleeve shirt with blue frontal prints) Actively Participating in Youth Communal Labour in his Constituency (Source: Chinnia's Gallery, 2021).

4.2.4. Conscientiousness

The accounts of Chinnia's party (NPP) and family respondents consistently demonstrated that Chinnia is highly conscientious in his dealings. Amidu Chinnia described himself as a task-oriented and responsible person who is always focused on getting things successfully done irrespective of opposition, distractions, impediments, or suppressions/oppressions. The conscientious personality of Amidu Chinnia was variously buttressed by all of Chinnia's co-patriots and family member-respondents when interviewed. In their considered views, Chinnia is honest, hardworking, goal-directed, ambitious, dutiful, responsible, trustworthy, meticulous, self-disciplined, habitually careful, well-composed, and morally upright personality. Honesty as a trait of Chinnia is synonymous with Dr. Hilla Limann's personality as reported by Banamini (2010); as cited in Dartey-Baah (2015). Although Chinnia's political opponents, when interviewed, generally agreed in principle that it partly took conscientiousness (hard work) for Chinnia to have won the Sissala East Parliamentary seat in 2020, they variously argued that incumbency and resources, in their opinions, were the key ingredients that have placed Chinnia an edge over his political opponents. They, however, commended Chinnia for his progressive political growth which has links with hard work, an element of conscientious personality.

4.2.5. Loyalty

The study found loyalty as one of the well-stressed personality dispositions of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia. Loyalty is often used to describe anyone or anything to whom or which one's heart could be persistently attached or devoted in terms of; policies, ideologies, moral values, brands, religions, politics, and others (Konvitz, 1973; as cited in Poulsen; 2020). Given this, Chinnia is generally portrayed by his party and family informants, whom the study contacted, to be one of the leading loyalists of NPP for over two decades. The NPP-informants consensually recounted that the available historical records of Amidu Chinnia's sustained political activism in the Sisaala enclave, Upper West Region and nationally, is enough concrete evidence of his unflinching loyalty to the progress of the NPP. The NPP-respondents, in unanimity, highlighted Chinnia's ability to timeously originate and committedly chair an NPP youth wing (Diglafuro Youth Wing), the first of its kind, to galvanise votes and popularise the NPP in the Sisaala enclave leading to Ghana's 2000 general elections, demonstrates his loyalty to NPP. In summation, one of the NPP's informants axioms that:

Chinnia's loyalty in leading the activities of the Diglafuro NPP youth wing and subsequent assumption of Constituency Deputy Secretary; Substantive Secretary Portfolio; TESCON Executive; two times NPP Parliamentary Candidate for the Sissala East Constituency, Deputy Upper West Regional Minister and now Member of Parliament for Sissala East Constituency and Deputy Minister of Sanitation and Water Resources vindicates his unparalleled loyalty to NPP. I think Chinnia's Deputy Ministerial appointments and

election as the current Member of Parliament of Sissala East Constituency, largely, has to do with his long-lasting loyal service to NPP and the confidence that such loyalty could inure to the benefit of his electorates. (NPP informant 3, personal communications, June 20, 2021)

Although Chinnia's political opponent, when interviewed, partly corroborated the views espoused by the NPP-respondents on Chinnia's loyalty to his party which has brought him this far, they, however, questioned Chinnia's loyalty to NPP during the campaign activities of 2008 and 2016 parliamentary elections in Sissala East Constituency when Chinnia respectively lost the two primaries and was not NPP's candidate on such counts. They accused Chinnia of not exhibiting enough loyalty in such elections probably because he was not the candidate for the elections. Besides that, Chinnia's political opponent agreed in principle that Chinnia is a staunch loyalist of NPP to the extent that he was always quick to support, what they described as, unpopular policies of NPP such as the E-Levy (electronic levy), a new tax regime (bill) adopted by the NPP-led government pending the approval of the legislative arm of Ghana. To Chinnia's political opponents, when the E-levy is passed, it would bring untold hardship to the constituents of Sissala East and all Ghanaians with Chinnia being an accomplice due to his public advocacy for the approval of the levy. The views expressed on loyalty as a personality disposition of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia and sufficiently authenticated by Chinnia's admirable political progress, contextually, suggests that loyalty is a principal trait requirement of political success.

4.3 Amidu Issahaku Chinnia's contributions to national development

The accounts of the respondents showed that Amidu Issahaku Chinnia is a professional teacher and a staunch political activist, who has made and continues to make significant contributions to the development of the Sissala enclave, Upper west region and Ghana at large. Chinnia's sacrificial but dedicated contributions to the education of many Ghanaian pupils and/or students when he was a classroom teacher, headteacher and officer of Ghana Education Service are worthy of acknowledgment. Chinnia indicated that some of his former students (names ethically withheld) have variously furthered their education to become professional nurses, teachers, security officers and many other responsible professionals in Ghana contributing their quotas to national development. To this end, Chinnia added that the joy and evidence of his contribution to national development as a teacher and for that matter, the case of every dedicated teacher, rested on the case that many of his former pupils/students have progressed to become not only responsible individuals but have occupied enviable national positions in civil and public services, politics, and entrepreneurship.

Also, Chinnia's contributions to national development as a young political activist in the Sisaala land in the Upper West Region of Northern Ghana were adequately recounted and unanimously corroborated by all the NPP-respondents, Chinnia's co-patriots. It was asserted by the NPP-respondents that Chinnia's contributions to national development as a political appointee (Assembly Member of Sissala District, 2005-2008; Deputy Upper West Regional Minister- 2017-2020, Deputy Minister of Sanitation and Water Resources-2021-till date) as well as Member of Parliament for Sissala East Constituency) were noticeably evident. Chinnia, during a town hall accountability forum to climax the commissioning of his newly established secretariat (MP's Office Complex) in Tumu on January 7, 2022, censused dozens of donations, projects, financial support, sponsorship and others extended to individuals and institutions during his first year in office as a member of parliament for Sissala East constituency. Some of such contributions as catalogued by Chinnia could be observed in Figure 5: A, B, C, D & E. First and famous, the construction and commissioning of MP's office in Tumu to serve as the central point where his constituents could easily lodge their developmental and other needs to him for redress.

The office came with an ancillary radio station registered as Sissala Radio (96.3FM) and described as one of the radio networks with the largest coverage in northern Ghana, primarily established to propel the development of the Sisaala land and Ghana by extension. Also, Chinnia is said to have lobbied from central government the construction and handing-over of 3- and 6-unit classroom blocks in Bugujan and Nabugujan, respectively, for

effective teaching and learning in the beneficiary communities. Chinnia equally donated medical equipment such as; pulse oximeter, Blood Pressure (BP) apparatus-wrist, gun thermometer, weighing scales, flexible rubber digital thermometer, blood glucose monitor with fifty (50) strips, lancets, and three laptop computers to the management of Tumu Municipal Hospital for good health delivery to his constituents and others, particularly in the midst of COVID-19 pandemic. Chinnia further added that, in his first year in office as MP, he had provided sponsorship to many students in and outside his constituency to study Law, Medicine, postgraduate, and bachelor's degree programmes in Ghana. He also made a donation of one hundred (100) sewing machines to hundred (100) ladies for vocational skills training and a cash donation of Two Thousand Ghana Cedis (Ghc 2000.00) to forty (40) other ladies to be trained in the production of liquid soap, and other liquid sanitisers. All 140 ladies were inhabitants of the Sissala East Constituency. Also, drilling and handing over of six (6) boreholes to Stadium residential area in Tumu, Sakai, Nabulo, Gwosi Lower, Gbenewisi communities with additional five (5) boreholes yet to be completed and handed over to beneficiary communities all totaling eleven (11) boreholes intended to alleviate the longstanding water challenges faced by the beneficiary communities. A donation of four (4) lorry tyres and Five Thousand Ghana Cedis (Ghc 5,000.00) was also made to Sissala East Municipal Directorate of Ghana Education Service for the servicing of one of their faulty vehicles for supervision and other official activities as well as a full-scale renovation of Sissala East Municipal office of Ghana Education Service to give it a facelift. Chinnia also stressed that he aided the employment of over a hundred youth in public and civil services in Ghana. In the house of parliament, Chinnia reported that he vocally and severally contributed to parliamentary businesses as a first-timer MP.

Given the recounts of Amidu Issahaku Chinnia's contributions to development in his first year in office as an MP, as herein espoused, it is clear that Chinnia is a development-oriented personality who is bent on doing everything within his might for the development of Sissala East Constituency and Ghana in general.

A: Chinnia MP's Office Complex with Ancillary Radio Station at Tumu.

B: Chinnia Donating One Hundred (100) Sewing Machines to Hundred (100) Ladies for Vocational Skills Training.

C: Chinnia Testing a Newly Drilled Borehole.

C: Newly Opened Road from Pina to Nitalu, Piina to Tanla

D: 6-Unit Classroom Block at Naabugujan

E: Renovated GES Office block at Tumu

Figure 5 (A, B, C, D & E): Some Photographic Evidence of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia's Developmental Initiatives of his One year in office as a Member of Parliament (Photo Credit: Chinnia's Gallery, 2022).

However, Chinnia's political opponents, when interviewed, underrated Chinnia's list of contributions to development, as herein espoused. They variously argued that donations could not and should not be enumerated as achievements since Chinnia's predecessors had all made donations. They further claimed that some of the projects are funded by the central government for which reason, Chinnia ought not to claim credit for their executions. Although they appreciated and commended Chinnia's move to establish an MP's office in the constituency, the first of its kind, they indicated their reservations that the office should have been fully established with his share of the MP's common fund to make it a permanent public office for succeeding MPs to use after Chinnia. However, they largely agreed with Chinnia on the issue of his proactiveness in facilitating a good number of youth employment in the NPP-led government some of whom are known political opponents of Chinnia. They added that much is expected of Chinnia and his NPP-led government in fixing the deplorable road network in the Sisaala enclave, reduction in the prices of agricultural inputs (fertilizer) and reduction in the rising cost of fuel and its rippling effect on the entire economy. Until that was done, Chinnia and his ruling party could not be said to have chalked any developmental success and would therefore lose the 2024 general elections.

5. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Grounded on biographical narrative design, the study singled out and documented the biography, personality traits and developmental contributions of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia as a young political activist in the Sisaala enclave of northern Ghana. Therefore, similar biographical narrative research could be conducted to bring to academia's limelight, the lives, times and contributions of other unsung distinguished political figures (young and old) and other legends in the Sisaala land, Ghana, Africa and the global landscape.

6. CONTRIBUTION TO THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The study stands to significantly contribute to the scientific community and future research as its findings add to the existing stock of scientific knowledge on qualitative biographical narrative research thereby serving as vital reference material to future biographical studies.

7. CONCLUSION

The study chronicled the biography of Amidu Isahaku Chinnia emphasising his unique personality dispositions and key developmental contributions as a young political activist of Sisaala land in Ghana. It was established that Amidu Isahaku Chinnia is a growing academic (Master of Philosophy and LLB degrees holder) and a staunch member of NPP in Ghana who currently serves as the MP for Sissala East Constituency and Deputy Minister of Sanitation and Water Resources. Although Chinnia's political prominence and stalwartness cannot be matched with the nationally known and documented political stalwarts in Ghana (Kwame Nkrumah, Kofi Abrefa Busia, Hilla Limann, Adu Boahen, Jerry John Rawlings and others), Chinnia could be said to have a humble beginning; has engendered various developmental initiatives, largely in his constituency (Sissala East); has gained prominence in his political party for which reason he had the privilege to be appointed twice by President Akufo Addo to serve as deputy minister of state. Chinnia could, therefore, be said to be a potential political stalwart in Ghana.

Also, with mixed viewpoints ably argued by the research participants, the study further found Chinnia to be a development-focused personality with positive dispositions that are in tandem with the five-factor personality model such as; emotional intelligence, assertiveness, openness, conscientiousness, and loyalty. Therefore, Chinnia stands to consolidate his political growth and fortunes if he sustains and promotes his positive personality dispositions while working on his weaknesses; dedicatedly works to unite the rank and file of his party in the Sissala East Constituency; addresses, through lobbying from central government, the major developmental needs of his constituents in the areas of roads, agriculture, education, health, and others, as well as provides loyal support to the NPP-led government of which he serves, to deliver its mandate to the people of Ghana as promised.

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